

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036640.

Recommendations for building a knowledge network for energy renovation

April 2025

Aggeli Aggeliki*

Aalborg University
Denmark

*agag@build.aau.dk

Suggested citation

Aggeli, A., Foulds, C., Crowther, A., Robison, R., Noreña Ospina, M., Weiser, P., Tobias, J., Koritar, Z., Bubulyte, L., Urbonaite, M., Tiernan R., Dennehy, L. 2025. *Recommendations for building a knowledge network for energy renovation*. Cambridge: SHARED GREEN DEAL. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15270076>

Introduction

The following set of recommendations have been co-created between the SHARED GREEN DEAL consortium partners and four local partners in the Efficient Renovations experiment stream. Below is a list of all the contributing partners:

Consortium research and practice partners:

- **Aalborg University:** Aggeliki Aggeli: agag@build.aau.dk
- **Anglia Ruskin University:** Chris Foulds: Chris.Foulds@aru.ac.uk ; Ami Crowther (ami.crowther@aru.ac.uk) ; Rosie Robison (rosie.robison@aru.ac.uk)
- **Women Engage in a Common Future (WECF):** Marcela Noreña Ospina: marcela.norena@wecf.org; Pia Wieser: pia.wieser@wecf.org

Local partners:

- **ECODES Zaragoza:** Javier Tobias: javier.tobias@ecodes.org <https://ecodes.org>
- **Habitat for Humanity Hungary:** Zsuzsanna Koritar: zsuzsanna.koritar@habitat.hu <https://habitat.hu/habitat-for-humanity-hungary/>
- **Let's Renovate the City, Vilnius, Lithuania:** Lina Bubulyte: lina.bubulyte@amiestas.lt <https://amiestas.lt/>, Monika Urbonaite: monika.urbonaite@amiestas.lt
- **Mayo County Council Louisburgh:** Rosarie Tiernan: rosarietiernan@gmail.com, Lorna Dennehy: lornadennehy@mayococo.ie

The recommendations also include feedback and inputs from participants (including citizens and professionals in the building industry) of the four knowledge networks, during the final events of the experiments, held in each location. The full process of co-creating these recommendations is presented and analysed in an upcoming journal publication.

How to read the recommendations:

The recommendations comprise of four stages:

Stage 1: Designing the network

Stage 2: Recruiting participants & designing activities

Stage 3: Running activities & facilitation

Stage 4: Knowledge sharing & dissemination

These stages mirror the framework upon which the Efficient Renovations experiment stream was generated, by the SHARED GREEN DEAL experiment team, in the beginning of the project. For further details on the Efficient Renovations experiment stream see: <https://sharedgreendeal.eu/resources/case-study-guides> (pp.20-26)

The table below provides an overview of all the categories of recommendations, as co-created by the partners of the SHARED GREEN DEAL project.

Following that, each Stage of the recommendations includes an initial description as well as a series of guiding statements (or questions) which can help define some of the issues encountered in each stage.

Stage	Recommendation
Stage 1: Designing the knowledge network	#1: Establish purpose and focus of the network
Stage 2: Recruiting participants & designing activities	#2: Define expertise
	#3: Reach out to groups in vulnerable situations (e.g households under/in danger of energy poverty)
	#4: Target professional members
	#5: Design & facilitate focused recruitment for events
Stage 3: Running activities & facilitation	#6: Setting up activities
	#7: Account for difference
	#8: Consider gender & intersectionality
	#9: Facilitation & presentation
Stage 4: Knowledge sharing & dissemination	#10: Name the network & find your audience
	#11: Networking
	#12: Media & Mediation
	#13: Storytelling and visualising 'invisible' groups

Stage 1: Designing the knowledge network

Stage 1 is a preparatory phase. Interested parties can get together and brainstorm about the conception of the knowledge network, such as the definition of its purpose, its focus, as well as the identification of who could be involved, such as which social groups might be relevant, and the kind of experiences and perspectives the network might involve.

Recommendation #1: Establish purpose and focus of the network

Recommendation #1 is set as a series of guiding questions, rather than guiding statements, as these might be more useful for those putting together the network, as practical and conceptual indicators. The questions are only indicative and can be shaped according to the specific context of the particular location and its characteristics.

- What are the local policy priorities for the residential energy efficiency sector?
- What does the local community want to build the network for?
- What are the different forms of know-how (e.g materials to touch, play with tech etc.) that can be explored through the network?
- Are there any specific challenges and subjects to handle? (e.g multi-apartment renovation and heating systems, facades, interactions with professionals etc.)
- How can the network embed and communicate the perspective that renovation is not just a technical practice but has many dimensions, i.e environmental, socio-cultural and political?
- How can people's lived experiences and perspectives become visible?
- What homes are hard-to-renovate locally? What are the local renovation professionals more experienced in delivering? What capacities are offered by supply chains?
- What are the target groups (e.g. those who want to receive knowledge and those who are willing to provide the knowledge)- Conduct a survey to find out
- How can you successfully co-create with the relevant communities to allow for the network's direction?

Stage 2: Recruiting participants & designing activities

Stage 2 is about the successful and inclusive recruitment of participants of a knowledge network, as well as the design and facilitation of activities relevant to recruitment. It brings to the attention of the organisers issues of expertise, inclusivity and outreach, particularly to groups who might be in vulnerable situations, such as energy poverty. It also highlights how to include actors from different sectors of the renovation practice, such as building professionals.

Recommendation #2: Define expertise

- Look for relevant partners, according to planned activities
- Have suitable and/or qualified people for the purpose of the activities
- Find the local 'agents', i.e people that are trusted within networks
- Choose a project that has benefits for the majority of the engaged community
- Identify different kinds of expertise e.g not only qualified professionals, but also include the lived and tacit experience of 'ordinary' people

Recommendation #3: Reach out to groups in vulnerable situations (e.g households under/in danger of energy poverty)

- Brainstorm ways to identify and reach groups in vulnerable situations in the relevant community
- Identify and involve social intermediaries/local leaders (i.e local people or actors with established relationships to the community) who people already trust. These are important actors for reaching out to communities
- Consider gender and intersectionality issues (e.g caregiving roles in the households or communities, considerations of who might have more limited time for attending events etc.) when recruiting
- Identify any structural exclusion characteristics related to e.g energy poverty
- Identify and build on personal contacts with households in vulnerable situations, through e.g local governments & their social departments or other actors who might have access to such citizen groups
- Consider different kinds of incentives for attracting citizens in vulnerable situations (even small incentives help-consult your local representatives to understand what would be best of each community)
- Use social media platforms (e.g Facebook groups or other media popular and accessible in the community or existing community forums or platforms) for attracting participants & collaborators

Recommendation #4: Target professional members

- Customise recruitment for professional members- they might have very different needs and preferences to citizen members

- Link to or include organisations' interests in the network, to help promote better recruitment in the network
- Consider the language and communication issues for professional members, which might be different to that of citizens-make sure you set clear definitions of the issues concerned
- Consider appropriate incentives for participation (particularly of professionals)
- Recruit retired professionals which might have more time and availability, even if they are less in touch with the latest know-how (current incentives, etc.).

Recommendation #5: Design & facilitate focused recruitment for events

- Don't underestimate the time required for recruitment- allow for plenty of time for organisation and recruitment
- Focus on insights from local leaders /people active in the relevant field and use their existing networks
- Find motivated local and like-minded organisations and work with them- they are a good starting point for recruiting local people
- Organise a grand event (e.g for opening the network)
- Give event participants attention, make them feel important
- Have clear incentives for each target group, including professionals and members in vulnerable situations even small incentives always help-make clear what these are (if any)
- Use and build on personal connections and existing networks, particularly when reaching hard-to-reach groups
- Be transparent with your expectations for network members
- Consider location and demographics' characteristics and challenges (e.g rural locations, travel times, accessibility, transport options/possibly offer free transport etc.)
- Keep in mind the season / weather conditions as they have an impact on activities
- Have flexible targets for recruitment- the network will be continuously changing rather than being static, people will come & go, and this should be considered in its design

Stage 3: Facilitating activities

Stage 3 refers to guidelines regarding the facilitation of the events and activities (planned in Stage 2), and practical insights about the inclusivity and engagement of these activities. It builds on the SHARED GREEN DEAL's local partners' past experiences and expertise on facilitating community events, as well as on empirical insights generated from running the SHARED GREEN DEAL Efficient Renovations experiment stream.

Recommendation #6: Setting up activities

- Be clear about the purpose of each activity
- Set the length of time for activities
- Allow people to 'tell their story'
- Organise thematic sessions (e.g financial and technical sessions, different typologies' sessions and 'how-to-plan' sessions)
- Set expectations in the beginning of each event (e.g recognise the equal value of layman expertise/everyday experience to that of professional trade)
- Divide sessions into smaller parts (e.g learning, sharing, knowledge-gained etc.)
- Balance fostering the active participation of vulnerable groups but also keeping it interesting/relevant for professional members
- Set up the room appropriately (e.g chairs etc.) to help give it a welcoming and accessible feel
- Schedule home-tours at different times of the day. Professional members in particular might want to stick to work hours (e.g 9-5) and citizens generally might prefer after work
- Give as much notice as possible for events such as home-tours (especially to professional members)
- Try to not 'compete' with other community events Include weekends and evenings for organising events. Most households prefer these, including professionals, when they know that there will be adequate attendance from households
- Consider length of activities (e.g 2 hrs might be too long for some)

Recommendation #7: Account for difference

- Make sure that group activities have a balanced mix of different experiences and expertise
- Consider groups within the network who might be at a different stage of renovation (e.g thinking, planning, performing etc.) and account for them
- Ask for feedback from participants (e.g what to improve, what went well, how to build things in the agenda)
- Enable hybrid participation in order to be more inclusive for those who cannot attend physically
- Offer options for those who are primary caregivers (e.g allow children at the venue)

Recommendation #8: Consider gender and intersectionality

- Decide (internally, in the organisers' group) who will monitor gendered behaviours/expressions/practices and power dynamics. This role would be to try and ensure inclusivity and appropriate design for this
- Actively engage women in the network by asking them questions
- Seek out women professionals to speak (in the network event) and share experiences

Recommendation #9: Facilitation and presentation

- Keep sessions informal, conversational and be mindful of the language used
- Observe power dynamics during interactions (e.g consider potential imbalance in the dynamics)
- Observe, and be mindful of, the pace of presentations (not too fast, not too slow)
- Make invisible technology visible by making it more accessible (e.g ventilation systems in or outside buildings if visiting renovation sites)
- Build in time for playing and touching technologies (during renovation site visits or home tours)
- Allow time for Q&A
- Make time outside formal events for socialising
- Ensure events are fun for people, especially if they occur during their leisure time (e.g provide drinks, gifts etc.)
- Allow and plan for (some/selected) activities to be run by network members themselves
- Allow regular breaks and pauses

Stage 4: Knowledge sharing / dissemination

Stage 4 refers to the different ways in which the network can share and disseminate its impact to other audiences, including its own members and to external actors who are interested in the process.

Recommendation #10: Name the network and find your audience

- Have a (clear) name for your initiative before dissemination
- Define the audience for the dissemination/ sharing of activities and understand what is relevant to them
- Ask network participants what has worked for them (and what has attracted them in the network)
- Communicate concrete recommendations to the audience
- Use social media platforms (e.g Facebook groups) not just for recruiting but for keeping members on board
- Develop accessible and easy to understand content in communications

Recommendation #11: Networking

- Present/share network activities with other projects (that organisers or other network members might be working on)
- Find ways to build trust in the network, by allowing people to tell their stories and give others the details of their experience—building faith that it can happen
- Recognise the value of connecting with similar networks and reach out

Recommendation #12: Media & Mediation

- Find the strengths of the organising group and use them (e.g who is good with people, who has a large network etc.)
- Use different media to reach out participants and other networks (e.g interpersonal communication, digital /social media, print media, tv, phone calls etc.)
- Interactive media, such as videos are more engaging to participants than text
- Contribute to events and activities of relevant professional bodies to disseminate and share the activities of the network (e.g trade shows, conventions, workshops etc.)
- Ask participants their preferences for communication (most accessible, familiar, easy-to-use media etc.)

Recommendation #13: Storytelling and visualising 'invisible' groups

- Share personal stories and experiences of members
- Visualise and tell the (successful) stories of 'invisible' groups of citizens in order to help others relate/engage
- Actively and regularly communicate positive feedback and successes of the network (internally and externally in the network)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036640.